

Supplementary information

Genome editing in almond: A CRISPR-based approach through hairy root transformation

Supplementary Table S1. List of oligonucleotides

Supplementary Table S2. List of all potential off-target sites predicted by the Cas-OFFinder tool in the almond genome (*P. dulcis* cv. Texas)

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Guides

(Esp31 restriction sites in red lower-case, cut site in red upper-case, guide sequence in green)

ERF74_guide1_fw	GTGcgtctcAATTGGCTTTCCAGCAGAGAAAGCAGGTTTgagacgCAC
ERF74_guide1_rev	GTGcgtctcCAAACCTGCTTTCTCTGCTGGAAAGCCAATTgagacgCAC
ERF74_guide2_fw	GTGcgtctcAATTGGGAATTCGCCAGCGCCCATGTTTgagacgCAC
ERF74_guide2_rev	GTGcgtctcCAAACCATGGGCGCTGGCGAATTCCTCAATTgagacgCAC
GAI_guide1_fw	GTGcgtctcAATTGGTACCGTTCACTATAACCCGTGTTTgagacgCAC
GAI_guide1_rev	GTGcgtctcCAAACACGGGTTTATAGTGAACGGTACCAATTgagacgCAC
GAI_guide2_fw	GTGcgtctcAATTGGCAACATATCGGAGAATGAGGTTTgagacgCAC
GAI_guide2_rev	GTGcgtctcCAAACCTCATCTCCGATATGTTGCCAATTgagacgCAC

Target loci amplification

ERF74_locus1_fw	TGTGGAGGTGCTATAATATCCGATTTTC
ERF74_locus1_rev	TCTCTAACATCAATCCACCCCTTTAAACC
ERF74_locus2_fw	CTCTACGACTGTGAAATCAGTGGAGTTC
ERF74_locus2_rev	CACTGAGTTGCCACCATCCTGAG
GAI_locus1_fw	TATCCCTATCCAGACCCGTCATC
GAI_locus1_rev	GAAGACGAGGTGAGAGGCAGAAGAC
GAI_locus2_fw	AAACCCACCACGATTCTTCGTCC
GAI_locus2_rev	TCGACTCAGTGAGCCATCACCG

RT-qPCR

Q ERF74_fw	GGAAAGCCCTCTCTGCTCGTA
Q ERF74_rev	CCTTGGGTCTCGGATCTCTGC
Q ACT_fw	TTGGAATGGAGGCTGCTGGTATT
Q ACT_rev	GCCTCCAATCCAGACGCTGT

Off-target analysis

ERF74_g1_Pd01_-16219319_fw	CCTTGGCTCATATACCTCATCACAT
ERF74_g1_Pd01_-16219319_rev	GTAAATCTCCCTACATTCTCTATGC
ERF74_g1_Pd03_-9068856_fw	CCAAGAACCTGCAAGAAGACATTG
ERF74_g1_Pd03_-9068856_rev	TCCTGAACTCATCTTTGGTGAC
ERF74_g1_Pd04_-9549693_fw	AAACTAAAGCTCACGCTCGGG
ERF74_g1_Pd04_-9549693_rev	GGATAACAATACCATCCTCGGC
ERF74_g2_Pd04_-22567141_fw	TTACAGTGGAGATCATTTCCCAAGC
ERF74_g2_Pd04_-22567141_rev	GAAGATAACGCCACACGCAGAC
ERF74_g2_Pd06_+3018280_fw	GACTCCTCCAGCGACGAAGAAG
ERF74_g2_Pd06_+3018280_rev	CGGCGTTAGGAAAGTTGGTGAC
ERF74_g2_Pd06_+3042881_fw	GACTCCTCCAGCGACGAAGAAG
ERF74_g2_Pd06_+3042881_rev	CGGCGTTAGGAAAGTTGGTGAC
GAI_g1_Pd07_+4850919_fw	CGAAGTAGCCTACCCTCTCAACTG
GAI_g1_Pd07_+4850919_rev	TCAGAAATCCTGAATCCGCCAT
GAI_g2_Pd01_+8709365_fw	GAGGCTCAAACGGTATCCAAA
GAI_g2_Pd01_+8709365_rev	TGACGAGTAAGGTATGGATTCTAC
GAI_g2_Pd02_-14236738_fw	GAGTAGAATCAGAGAAGGTGCTTG
GAI_g2_Pd02_-14236738_rev	CGCAATGATTCCATCTCTCTTT
GAI_g2_Pd08_-6198750_fw	TGCTTCTTCTTCAATGCTATATGTGC
GAI_g2_Pd08_-6198750_rev	CTAACATCCGATAAATGCTTGGTG

Supplementary Table 2. List of all potential off-target sites predicted by the Cas-OFFinder tool in the almond genome (*P. dulcis* cv. Texas). The PAM motif is highlighted in bold, and the mismatched bases to the original target sites are shown in red lowercase letters. Mutation rate represents the number of hairy roots with mutations divided by the total number of tested hairy roots. MMs, number of mismatches. ^a, homologous regions (250 bp up- and down-stream to the target site). ^b, amplified off-target site in the studied cultivar Vairo that differed from the *in silico* predicted off-target in cultivar Texas. Consequently, the corresponding genomic regions were sequenced in wild-type roots of the studied cultivar and compared to those from hairy roots. n.a., not analyzed.

gRNA	Putative off-target locus	Sequence	MMs	Mutation rate
ERFguide1	Pd01: -16219319	aTTTCCAGCAGAA AAAA CAG TGG	3	0/8
	Pd03: -9068856	gTTTCCAGgAGAGAA tGCAGTGG	3	0/8
	Pd04: -9549693	agTTCCAGCAGAGAA gGCAGGGG	3	0/8
	Pd06: -23078226	aTTT ga AtCAGAGAA AGCAGAGG	4	n.a.
	Pd08: +3965791	agTTCCAG ctGAGAAgGCAGGGG	4	n.a.
	Pd03: -9062785	gTTTCCAGgAGAG gAtGCAGTGG	4	n.a.
	Pd03: -6823832	gTTTCCAGaAGAGAA gGaaAGG	4	n.a.
	Pd07: -17360615	tTTTCCAGCAGAc AAgGCAaAGG	4	n.a.
	Pd03: +12342957	Ca TcCCT GCAGAGAA GCAtGGG	4	n.a.
	Pd04: -4643756	CT ctGCAa CAG tGAAAGCAGCGG	4	n.a.
	Pd04: -22874809	CT gttt AGCAGAA AAAGCAGGGG	4	n.a.
	Pd03:+12628686	CT ga CCAGCA aAGAAAGaAGAGG	4	n.a.
	Pd05: +6915268	CTTT tcat CA aAGAAAtCAGTGG	4	n.a.
	Pd05: -6066496	CTTT aCAaa aCAGAA AGCAGAGG	4	n.a.
	Pd05: -6071075	CTTT aCAaa aCAGAA AGCAGAGG	4	n.a.
	Pd02: +12590413	CTTT gCAcc CAG AgAAGCAGAGG	4	n.a.
	pdulcis26_s0686: +62241	CTTT gCAcc CAG AgAAGCAGAGG	4	n.a.
	Pd07: +759994	CTTT gCAGCAGAGAtta CAG GGG	4	n.a.
	Pd08: -17626304	CTTT ca AGCAGAG AtAGgcTGG	4	n.a.
	Pd04: +7685049	CTT ggc AG ctGAGAAAGctGAGG	4	n.a.
Pd06: -28376323	CTT gCa AGCA aAGAAAaCAGAGG	4	n.a.	
Pd05: +1381635	CTT ccc AtCAGAG AgAGtAGTGG	4	n.a.	
Pd08: +11186703	CTT ccc AGCA aAgAAGCAGTGG	4	n.a.	
Pd03: +18792526	CTT ccc AGCAG tGAAAcCAtGGG	4	n.a.	
Pd03: -4591175	CT atC aAGCAGAG AAAcTGGG	4	n.a.	
Pd08: +18797158	C TTTCCAGa AG tAAAGctGTGG	4	n.a.	
ERFguide2	Pd04: -22567141	GGAg tCCGC aAGCG gCCATGGG	4	0/8
	Pd06: +3018280	GGAg tCCGCC gCG aCCATGGG	4	0/8 ^a
	Pd06: +3042881	GGAg tCCGCC gCG aCCATGGG	4	0/8 ^a
GAIguide1	Pd07: +4850919	TACa GTTCg CTATA caCCGTGG	4	0/2 ^b
GAIguide2	Pd01: +8709365	aa AA ctg ATCGGAGAA TGAGTGG	4	0/2 ^b
	Pd02: -14236738	GCAA aatATaa GA aatGAGAGG	4	0/2 ^b
	Pd08: -6198750	GC atg ATATCG aAGAATGaaAGG	4	0/2